

Gravitational Waves and Gamma-rays in the LIGO, Virgo, and KAGRA O4 and O5 Observing Runs

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Talk outline

- Science Examples
- GW timeline for O4, O5
- GWs and INTEGRAL and IPN

- GRB 221009A (if time)

Science with GWs and GRBs

- Behavior of speed-of-light jets
 - Jet formation
 - Jet structure
- Origin of the elements
 - Current contribution to r-process
 - History of r-process enrichment
- Neutron star equation of state
 - **Maximum NS mass**
 - Precise mass-radius measure
 - Metastable neutron star lifetime
- Standard Siren cosmology
 - Hubble constant
 - Nature of neutrinos
 - Shape of the universe
 - Dark energy equation of state
- Fundamental physics
 - Lorentz Invariance (including **speed of gravity**)
 - GW polarization
 - Extra large dimensions
 - **Gravitational parity**

NS Mergers

System	BNS → Increasing Mass				NSBH	
Class	Stable	SMNS	HMNS	Prompt Collapse	Light	Heavy
Progenitor						
Remnant						
Jets						
Prompt SGRB						
SGRB Afterglow						
Ejecta						
Kilonova						

Potentially in ~ 2030 , but rare

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Kilonova						7

Bluer and faster

Generic arguments: The longer the remnant is a neutron star

- The more (lanthanide-free) dynamical ejecta
- Lower overall lanthanide fraction given neutrino production from the object itself

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Option 1: No Jets

Never observe a short GRB (or afterglow) after a low-mass GW-detected NS merger

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SGRB Afterglow						
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Kilonova						

Option 2: Plateaus

Rastinejad et al. arXiv:2204.10864
SGRB w/ EE and kilonovae

But kilonovae not very blue

Also

Zhu et al. ApJL 936.1 2022

Troja et al. arXiv:2209.03363

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Science: Speed of Gravity

Burns *Living Reviews in Relativity* 23 4 (2020)

Population sensitivity scales as \sqrt{N}

Science: Gravitational Parity Conservation

N

The Importance of GW-GRB Joint Localizations

Petrov et al. ApJ 924 2 (2022)

- GW localizations improve, but less than previously thought
- This is due to adapting reporting criterion from the GW Network
- GW-GRB Events will be systematically further away, and thus more poorly localized

Joint Localizations, LVK+GBM/BAT

Fermi+INTEGRAL Annulus

Fermi-GBM

LIGO+Virgo

LVK alerts will be automatically associated to Fermi-GBM and Swift-BAT triggers in O4, the localizations combined, and distributed through the LVK alert stream

LIGO + Fermi-GBM
LIGO+Virgo

- Swift-BAT localizations are $\sim 3'$
- Fermi-GBM localizations vastly reduce \sim half of LVK localizations in O4
- Expect ~ 1 joint detection

The InterPlanetary Network (IPN): Past and Present

- 5* decades old, ~70 members
 - 1967 – Vela triangulation
 - ~1978 – 1992; Organizers: Kevin Hurley
 - 1992 – 2021; Organizers: Kevin Hurley, Russian Scientists
 - Key Members: AGILE, **Bepi-Colombo**, CALET, CGRO, Fermi, GECAM, Insight, INTEGRAL, Konus, Mars Odyssey, MESSENGER, RHESSI, Swift, Suzaku
 - 2022 - ; Organizers: Eric Burns, Dmitry Svinkin
 - Future instruments: StarBurst, COSI, **Psyche**, **MEGANE**
- Discoveries
 - >3500 direct citations, thousands more enabled
 - Separation of GRBs, soft gamma-ray repeaters (SGRs)
 - Anisotropy of SGRs, association with supernova remnants
 - Discovery of magnetars
 - Separation of short GRBs from neutron star mergers from extragalactic magnetar giant flares

Svinkin et al. 2021 Nature 589 221

Putting it together: a combined GRB alert stream

- Automatic association of reported GRB triggers
- Automatic combination of autonomous localizations
- Automatic annuli calculation immediately after data is available
 - Likely limited to manual at O4 start
 - **Fermi+INTEGRAL after ~10 min**
- Distribution to wider community with coherent information
- **Prioritization ranking**

Fermi+INTEGRAL Annulus

Fermi-GBM

LIGO+Virgo

Joint Localizations, GBM and Fermi+INTEGRAL

Note this is a biased sample

- From 2nd IPN catalog of Konus short GRBs
 - Approximately the top 1/3rd in brightness for Konus GRBs
- ~8.5x reduction in general
- Can be done in (near) real-time
- These maps can be passed through the LVK stream, and in most cases reduce the follow-up region by >x10
- Or to a GRB-only stream

Updated
16 June 2022

Joint Localizations, GBM and Fermi+INTEGRAL

Predicted GW-GRB (Fermi-GBM) Rates for O4

- Limitations:
 - GW interferometer sensitivity
 - GRB monitor sensitivity
- Benefits:
 - Face-on events are louder in GWs
 - ~x2 gain in searchable volume using seeded (targeted) searches
- One estimate for BNS GW-GRBs from LVK arXiv: 2111.03608:

$$R_{\text{GW-GRB}}^{\text{O4}} = 1.04^{+0.26}_{-0.27} \text{ yr}^{-1}$$

0-2 w/ Poisson uncertainty, neglects sub-threshold detections

Burns 2020 LRR 23 4
 Pulling from:
 Schutz 2011 CQG 28:125023
 Fong et al. 2015 ApJ 815 102

GRB 221009A

Credit: A. Goldstein (USRA)

Contact me if interested in a coordinated journal release, and potential broad collaborative papers

Summary

- High energy observations are critical to understand neutron star mergers
- It is critical to have INTEGRAL online in O4
- Probably also for O5
- And long enough for contemporaneous observations with COSI